

Identification of environmental water requirements for optimizing water use allocation in Cicatih watersheds, Sukabumi District, West Java

Popi Rejekiningrum

Indonesian Center for Agricultural Land Resources Research and Development

Indonesian Agency for Agricultural Research and Development

Jl. Tentara Pelajar No. 12 Bogor, Telp. 0251-8323012, hp. 08128027623,

Coresponding author: popirejeki@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Increasing water in the Cicatih watershed for various sectors has resulted higher pressure and competition in using water resources, which led to open conflicts between water users. Conflicts generally occur when there are parties who feel their rights are taken unfairly, so the parties' water use limits need to be known openly, including mandatory water for environmental water requirement. The use of this water for transportation, city flushing, recharging lakes, rivers etc. Calculation of environmental water requirement is generally based on minimum flow in the river that provides a level of protection for the aquatic environment. The science of environmental flows is relatively new. The most commonly used method is Tennant Method which recommended that minimum flow relative to the mean annual flow/MAF and minimum flows in the stream aims to provide a level of protection to the aquatic environment. Results of analysis of environmental water requirement in the Cicatih watershed generally tend to increase. Environmental water requirement across the Cicatih watershed covering 15 Subdistrict in 2017 reached 55.169.521 m³; while the projections for 2020 and 2030, respectively 55.418.394 m³ and 55.919.162 m³ with an average 0,3% increase per year. Among 15 sub-districts within the Cicatih watershed area, the greatest requirement is in Nagrak Sub-district which reaches 6,833,146 m³ in 2017, with projections for 2020 and 2030 of 6,863,971 m³ and 6,925,995 m³, respectively. Information of environmental water requirement is an important consideration in term of optimizing the allocation of water requirement for various sectors (domestic, agricultural, industrial), because this water requirement shall be fulfilled before the water requirement of other sectors are fulfilled.

Key words: *trend analysis of water requirement, optimizing the use of water, optimal water sharing, environmental water requirement*

INTRODUCTION

Environmental water requirements are included as mandatory (committed flow). This water is used for transportation, city flushing, lake filling, river maintenance and so on. Water use for the environment and ecology is relatively small compared to the needs of other sectors, but continues to grow, includes artificial wetlands, artificial lakes intended for natural habitats, conservation of fish animals, and release of water from reservoirs to help lay eggs. Furthermore, the use of water for recreation, for the environment and ecology include non-consumer use, but also reduces the availability of water for other needs somewhere at a certain time (Tharme, 2003).

Water use for the environment is analogous to environmental flow. The definition of environmental flow is the water system provided in rivers, wetlands or coastal zones to maintain ecosystems and their use (Dyson et al., 2004). This definition is updated and has been included in the 'Brisbane Declaration' (2007), which the flow of the environment describes the quantity, quality and time of water flow needed to maintain freshwater and estuarine ecosystems and human life and welfare that depend on this ecosystem.

Other definitions and terms about environmental flows exist, includes minimum flows in the river and ecology. However, the definition above and the term 'environmental flow' are the only ones that truly cover holistic concepts.

The conditions of aquatic ecosystems and services are basically a socio-political decision. The desired ecosystem conditions can be regulated (for example with international laws or conventions), and the environmental flows is the water system required to maintain the ecosystem. The flow of the environment allocated to the river system needs to be negotiated between water users. In this case, the ecosystem conditions produced are determined by negotiated and 'desired' environmental streams.

Determination of environmental flow requirements can take two fundamentally different approaches depending on the intended purpose, namely: (1) Whether ecosystem conditions must be maintained and how much water is required for this, (2) How much water does the community allocate to the ecosystem and whether the ecosystem conditions producing are maintained by the given water allocation, and this condition is desirable and adequate.

The science of environmental flows is relatively new. The development of environmental flows assessment (EFA) began in the United States in the late 1940s and developed during the 1970s, mainly as a result of new environmental and freshwater laws that accompanied the era of dam construction in the United States. Outside the United States, the development of the EFA methodology only

grew significantly in the 1980s. Australia and South Africa are the most developed countries in the development and application of EFA.

In a recent review of the international EFA, Tharme (2003) records 207 different EFA methodologies in 44 countries (America, Europe, Africa, Asia, Australia). Some categorization of methodology, three of which are shown in Table 1.

The minimum flows in the river aim to provide a level of protection for the aquatic environment. The level of protection is represented by measures such as proportions of historical flow, wet circumference or suitable habitat. Minimum flow assessment conflicts from different methods of instream flow can be debated from the results of different environmental objectives and levels of protection (Jowett 1997).

Several studies conducted by Tennant (1976), and Fraser (1978), Miljoestyrelsen (1979), Beecher (1990), Arthington et al., (1992), and Katz (2006) in Jowett (1997) and Reiser et al., (1989) calculated that 10% of the average flow provides minimum protection and 30% of the average flow is satisfactory.

In Indonesia, the analysis of surface water availability uses dependable flow as a reference. The most important role in the study is the record of river flow discharge. The recording must be continuous within a period of time that can be used for the implementation of water supply activities. If water tapping will be carried out from an unspoiled river, it is necessary to record data from long periods of low flow, so that the reliability of the water supply can be known.

Several studies have calculated water requirements for the environment based on minimum flows in rivers that provide a level of protection for the aquatic environment. The research was conducted in Kali Kuning, Sleman, Yogyakarta, taking into account the population growth rate, the contribution of the agricultural, drinking water, industry and environment sectors, as well as the sustainable potential of using springs, hence it was determined that the agricultural sector was allocated 50% of the debit from the spring, 35% for drinking water and industry, while the remaining 15% was for environmental purposes. Perum JasaTirta II, which is responsible for managing and distributing the water use of the Jatiluhur reservoir, establish that the allocation for the agricultural sector is 78% of total, domestic disbursement of 7%, industry 5%, hydro electricity 2%, and the remaining 3% for the sector fisheries and flushing (Sosiawan, 2005).

The objectives of this activity are: (1) identification of water availability in the cicatih watershed, (2) identify of environmental water requirements, (3)

projected of environmental water requirements, and (4) optimization of optimal water allocation.

Table1. Three categories of EFA methodologies

Organisation	Categorization of EFA	Sub-category	Example
IUCN (International Union for Conservation of Nature and Natural Resources (Dyson et al. 2003))	Methods	Look-up tables	Hydrological (e.g. Q95 Index) Ecological (e.g. Tennant Method)
		Desk-top analyses	Hydrological (e.g. Richter Method) Hydraulic (e.g. Wetted Perimeter Method) Ecological
		Functional analyses	BBM, Expert Panel Assessment Method, Benchmarking Methodology
		Habitat	PHABSIM Expert Team Approach, stakeholder Approach (expert and non-expert) IFIM, DRIFT
World Bank (Brown & King, 2003)	Prescriptive approaches	Hydrological Index	Tennant Method
		Hydraulic Rating Expert Panels	Wetted Perimeter Method
		Holistic Approaches	BBM
IWMI (Tharme, 2003)	Interactive approaches	Hydrological index methods	IFIM DRIFT
		Hydraulic rating methods	Tennant Method Wetted Perimeter Method
		Habitat simulation	IFIM
		Holistic methodologies	BBM DRIFT Expert Panel Benchmarking Methodology

Source: Tharme (2003)

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The most commonly used method is the Tennant method (Tennant 1976 in Jowett 1997, Marchand 2003, Kilgour et al., 2005, Korsgaard 2006). The Tennant method recommends that the minimum flow be set relative to the annual average flow (MAF) as shown in Table 2.

The mainstay discharge is the minimum flow of the river for fulfilled possibilities that have been determined (KIMPRASWIL 2000 in Bappenas 2006). The method used to determine the mainstay discharge is the ranking statistical method using the Weibull formula. The analysis procedure starts by sorting the

data series from the largest order to the smallest. The analysis procedure begin by sorting the data series from the largest order to the smallest. Next ranking begins with the first rank (m = 1) for the biggest data and so on.

Table 2. Water use for fish, wildlife, recreation, and related environmental resources

Description for general conditions of river discharge for parameter ¹	Recommended base flow ² as an average annual flow percentage	
	October-March	April-September
Flushing (maximum)	200	200
Optimum	60-100	60-100
Outstanding	40	60
Excellent	30	50
Good	20	40
Fair	10	30
Poor	10	10
Severe Degradation	< 10	<10

Source: Jowet (1997)

Note:¹Description for general conditions of river discharge for all parameters listed

²Base flow is considered as the lowest steady flow

Some reliable probability values are as follows:

- a. for drinking water : 99%
- b. for hydroelectric power plant : 85-90%
- c. for industrial water supply : 88-95%
- d. for irrigation water supply
- semi-humid climate : 70-85%
- dry climate : 80-90%

For environmental use there are no provisions of the mainstay debit calculation, so for this study the use for the environment is calculated by adopting the Tennant (1976) formula with the following equation:

$$W_L^D(t) = Q_{\min}(t) \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where: W_L^D = environmental water requirement
 Q_{\min} = minimum flow
 t = time

Overall the total water requirement for agriculture, domestic, industry and environment are presented in the following equation:

$$W_T^D(t) = W_P^D(t) + W_I^D(t) + W_S^D(t) + W_L^D(t) \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

- Where:
- W_T^D = total water requirement
 - W_P^D = domestic water requirement
 - W_I^D = industry water requirement
 - W_S^D = agriculture water requirement
 - W_L^D = environmental water requirement
 - t = time

The minimum flow is a base flow which is an important component in hydrographs derived from groundwater and/or subsurface storage that seep into the river channel, regardless of rainfall variability. So if in the dry season, the river flow consists only of base flow (Smakhtin 2001, McCuen 1998).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the analysis of environmental water requirements are calculated based on the minimum flow in the Cicatih watershed currently presented in Figures 1 and 2.

The projected environmental water requirements in 2020 and 2030 is presented in Figure 3-6.

Figure 1. Fluctuations in environmental water requirements in the Cicatih watershed in 2017

Figure 2. Environmental water requirements in each district in the Cicatih watershed in 2017

Figure 3. Fluctuations in environmental water requirements in the Cicatih watershed in 2010

Figure 4. Environmental water requirements in each district in the Cicatih watershed in 2020

Figure 5. Fluctuations in environmental water requirements in the Cicatih watershed in 2030

Figure 6. Environmental water requirements in each district in the Cicatih watershed in 2030

The results shows that the environmental water requirement in the Cicatih watershed tends to increase. The total environmental water requirement at this time (2017) reaches 55,169,521 m³, while the projection of total environmental water requirement in 2020 and 2030 is 55,418,394 m³ and 55,919,162 m³, respectively. Table 3 presents the distribution of water requirement for 15 sub-districts in the Cicatih watershed.

Distribution of environmental water requirement of 15 sub-districts within the Cicatih watershed shows that Nagrak sub-district is the biggest requirement which reaches 6,833,146 m³ at present, with projections for 2020 and 2030 of 6,863,971 m³ and 6,925,995 m³, respectively. While the least requirement is in Cidahu sub-district which reaches 1,415,437 m³, with projections for 2020 and 2030 of 1,421,823 m³ and 1,434,670 m³, respectively.

Information of environmental water requirement is an important consideration in the effort to optimize the allocation of water use for various sectors (domestic, agriculture, industry), because this water requirement must be fulfilled before the priority requirement in other sectors are fulfilled for optimal water sharing.

Table 3. Water requirement distribution of 15 sub-district in the Cicatih watershed

No	Sub-District	2017	2020	2030
1	Bojonggenteng	2,391,601	2,402,390	2,424,098
2	Caringin	3,107,455	3,121,473	3,149,679
3	Cibadak	6,361,334	6,390,030	6,447,771
4	Cicantayan	3,986,002	4,003,983	4,040,164
5	Cicurug	2,391,601	2,402,390	2,424,098
6	Cidahu	1,415,437	1,421,823	1,434,670
7	Cikembar	6,361,334	6,390,030	6,447,771
8	Cikidang	2,586,834	2,598,503	2,621,984
9	Cisaat	1,643,209	1,650,622	1,665,537
10	Kadudampit	3,514,189	3,530,042	3,561,940
11	Kalapanunggal	3,400,304	3,415,643	3,446,507
12	Nagrak	6,833,146	6,863,971	6,925,995
13	Parakansalak	2,830,875	2,843,645	2,869,341
14	Parungkuda	1,984,866	1,993,820	2,011,837
15	Warungkiara	6,361,334	6,390,030	6,447,771
	Cicatih Watershed	55,169,521	55,418,394	55,919,162

Determination of optimal water sharing can be regulated by local/regional/international laws or conventions through negotiations between water users. In Figure 7-10 presented lesson learned of optimal water sharing in Jatiluhur Reservoir, Kali Kuning, Cicatih Watershed, and Bengawan Solo Watershed.

Figure 7. Optimal water allocation of Jatiluhur Reservoir

Figure 8. Optimal water allocation of Kali Kuning

Figure 9. Optimal water allocation of Cicatih watershed

Figure 10. Optimal water allocation of Cicatih watershed

CONCLUSIONS

The total environmental water requirement in the Cicatih watershed at this time (2017) reaches 55,169,521 m³, while the projected in 2020 and 2030 is 55,418,394 m³ and 55,919,162 m³ respectively. The largest environmental water requirement is in Nagrak Sub-district which reaches 6,833,146 m³ for the time being, with projections for 2020 and 2030 of 6,863,971 m³ and 6,925,995 m³ respectively. While the least requirement is in Cidahu Subdistrict which reaches 1,415,437 m³, with projections for 2020 and 2030 amounting to 1,421,823 m³ and

1,434,670 m³.

The results of the analysis of environmental water requirements are an important consideration to optimize the allocation of water use for various other sectors (domestic, agriculture, industry), because this water requirement must be fulfilled before the priority requirements in other sectors are fulfilled. In an effort to determine optimal water sharing, it is necessary to allocate water use for all sectors, especially the use of water for the environment to anticipate conflicts over water use.

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